

Proof of the Goldbach Conjecture Using the Reverse Corresponding Coincidence Number Axes Method

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Abstract: The Goldbach conjecture is a difficult mathematical problem that has remained unsolved worldwide for over 300 years. To enable the final proof of the Goldbach conjecture, this paper innovatively constructs, for the first time in the world, the "reverse corresponding coincidence number axis" and the resulting "coincidence number sequence," opening up a new pathway for proving the Goldbach conjecture. By investigating and analyzing the properties of the coincidence number sequences, three lemmas are proposed and rigorously demonstrated. Based on relevant mathematical principles and theorems, and utilizing an improved Eratosthenes sieve method, this study provides a detailed, rigorous, and precise demonstration and comparative demonstration of the Goldbach conjecture. The key result is finally obtained: in every coincidence number sequence that takes an arbitrary even number n greater than 4 as its "Halt number," there exists at least one "prime coincidence number" (i.e., both corresponding addends are odd primes). Furthermore, the expression $\frac{p}{2} - 2$ (where p is the largest odd number not exceeding \sqrt{n}) is derived, which can circumvent the problem of "unknown primes," thereby fully proving that the Goldbach conjecture holds true.

Keywords: Goldbach's conjecture; reverse corresponding coincidence number axis; coincident numbers; coincidence number sequence; prime coincidence number

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Symbol Explanation:

(a, b) denotes the greatest common divisor of a and b .

【】 indicates horizontal notation for coincident numbers.

0 Introduction

Goldbach's Conjecture:

- a) Every even number greater than 4 can be expressed as the sum of two odd primes;
- b) Every odd number greater than 7 can be expressed as the sum of three odd primes.

The Goldbach Conjecture is a mathematical problem that remains unsolved worldwide to this day. Since its proposal in 1742, many outstanding mathematical experts and insightful individuals across the globe have striven relentlessly to prove it. They have endured immense hardships, made unremitting efforts, and continuously sought verification. Although they achieved one significant result after another, none ultimately succeeded in proving the Goldbach Conjecture. In 1966, *Science Bulletin* (No. 17) publicly published the paper by Chinese mathematician Chen Jingrun proving the Goldbach Conjecture: "On Expressing Even Numbers as the Sum of a Prime and a Product of at Most Two Primes" (abbreviated as "1+2"). Building on this, Chen Jingrun provided detailed proofs and refinements to this paper. In April 1973, the improved version of Chen's paper, "On the representation of a large even integer as the sum of a prime and the product of at most two primes," was published in *Scientia Sinica* (Chinese Science), a journal hosted by the Chinese Academy of Sciences. This became a milestone in the research of the Goldbach Conjecture, yet it remained one step away from the final proof.

It is said that there is now a consensus within the Chinese mathematical community: the path previously taken to prove the Goldbach Conjecture can no longer be pursued.

However, the dearly departed Goldbach must still be looking down from the heavens, watching to see who among future generations will finally pluck this brightest jewel from mathematics' crown.

In 1978, the magazine *People's Literature* published Xu Chi's reportage "The Goldbach Conjecture". This ignited in Yao Xingzhi a strong desire to prove the Goldbach Conjecture! He was determined to pluck this brightest pearl from the crown of mathematics and win glory for our great motherland!

Yao Xingzhi is an amateur mathematician who has enjoyed solving challenging mathematical problems since childhood. Beginning in 1980, utilizing his spare time after work, during over 40 years of arduous exploration into the Goldbach conjecture, although he took many detours due to a lack of relevant knowledge and also went astray because his knowledge was not comprehensive enough. However, Yao Xingzhi did not become disheartened or give up; instead, he grew more resilient with each setback. In the course of continuous exploration, he was very fortunate to discover the "reverse corresponding coincidence number axis." Utilizing the remarkably concise "reverse corresponding coincidence number axis" method, he pioneered and opened up a new path to prove the Goldbach conjecture. Through the coincidence number sequences formed by the "reverse corresponding coincidence number axis," and employing the modified Eratosthenes sieve method, Yao Xingzhi, after rigorous derivation and verification, proved that any even number greater than 4 can be expressed as the sum of two odd primes; simultaneously, he also proved that any odd number greater than 7 can be expressed as the sum of three odd primes. Thereby, he ultimately proved the validity of the Goldbach conjecture!

Yao Xingzhi's first draft, "Proof of the Goldbach Conjecture," only after passing the extremely rigorous, comprehensive, and meticulous internal review by the highly accomplished and very famous number theory expert Professor Liu Baoxiang from Hebei Province, the strict external review by two outstanding external mathematics experts, and the strict examination by the editor-in-chief, was it able to be publicly

published in Issue 4, 2002 of the *Journal of Hebei Institute of Technology*. To this day, no dissenting opinions have been seen!

Since the public publication of "Proof of the Goldbach Conjecture" in the Journal of Hebei Institute of Technology, Yao Xingzhi has continuously conducted further detailed proofs and refinements:

- 1 Supplemented and added detailed proofs for each step.
- 2 Proposed three related lemmas and conducted rigorous arguments for them.
- 3 Newly added a third step of proof.
- 4 Newly added a "Comparative Verification" section occupying substantial space.
- 5 Added extensive new content, including a proof of part (b) of the Goldbach conjecture, among others.

This process culminated in the second draft, titled "Proof of the Goldbach Conjecture Using the Reverse Corresponding Coincidence Number Axis Method", which enhanced the rigor and precision of every step of the proof.

The salient characteristic of this paper is innovation! Many of the nouns, terminology, concepts, and fundamental methods presented are unprecedented in mathematical literature, both Chinese and foreign.

1 Basic Theories and Theorems Related to This Paper

1.1 The number of prime numbers is infinite ^[3].

1.2 Analytic number theory ^[2].

1.3 If $a \leq n$ and a is not a prime, then a is **necessarily** divisible by a prime

number not greater than \sqrt{n} [1][3].

1.4 The Eratosthenes sieve method [3] is a fundamental method for finding prime numbers.

1.5 Let a, b, c be positive integers. When $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, the equation $ax + by = c$ certainly has integer solutions. All integer solutions can be expressed as:

$$x = x_0 + bt, \quad y = y_0 - at, \quad \text{where } t = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \dots [1][3].$$

1.6 Additive number theory [4].

2 Definition of Fundamental Concepts; Properties of Coincidence

Number Sequences

Reverse corresponding coincidence number axis: one natural number axis ox and another identical natural number axis oy are taken, and they are reverse-correspondingly coincided together, forming a new coincidence number axis xy , as shown in the figure.

Coincident numbers: two corresponding numbers, representing the addition of these two numbers in the form of mutual correspondence. For example, any one coincident number **【1,19】** on the coincidence number axis xy , represents the addition of the two corresponding numbers 1 and 19. In such a horizontally represented coincident number, the left number 1 is the corresponding number in ox , the right number 19 is the corresponding number in oy .

Coincidence number sequence: A continuous sequence composed of coincident numbers arranged in order. For example, the sequence arranged from left to right on

the coincidence number axis xy : **【1,19】**, **【2,18】**, **【3,17】**, ... **【20,0】** is a complete coincidence number sequence.

Halt number: A coincident number in which one of the two corresponding addends is zero. For example, **【20, 0】** on the coincidence number axis xy . Since for any natural number n , $n + 0 = n$, the halt number is precisely the number that corresponds to 0. This paper only discusses coincidence number sequences in which the halt number is even.

Even coincident numbers: A coincident number in which both corresponding addends are even. For example, **【2,18】** , **【4,16】** , etc. on the coincidence number axis xy . Even coincident numbers include the halt number.

Composite coincident numbers: A coincidence number in which at least one of the two corresponding addends is an odd composite number. For example, **【9,11】** , **【25,55】** , etc.

Prime coincidence number: A coincidence number in which both of the two corresponding addends are odd prime numbers. For example, **【3,17】** , **【7,13】** , **【13,7】** , etc. on the coincidence number axis xy .

Pseudo-prime coincidence number: between the two corresponding addends, one of them is 1, and the other is an odd prime number. For example, **【1,19】** , **【19,1】** on the coincidence number axis xy .

It is evident that coincident number sequences possess the following properties:

2.1 In the same coincidence number sequence, the total number of coincident numbers equals the halt number of this sequence.

2.2 For all coincident numbers in the same coincidence number sequence, the sum of the two corresponding addends is constant and equal to the halt number.

2.3 In every coincidence number sequence where an arbitrary even number greater than 4 serves as the halt number, since the halt number corresponds to an even number and 0, it follows that in all other coincident numbers, even numbers can only correspond to even numbers, and odd numbers can only correspond to odd numbers.

2.4 In every coincidence number sequence where an arbitrary even number greater than 4 serves as the halt number, all coincident numbers can only be categorized as: even coincident numbers, composite coincident numbers, prime coincidence numbers, and pseudo-prime coincidence numbers.

2.5 In any coincidence number sequence, the number of corresponding numbers in ox and oy respectively equals the number of coincident numbers.

2.6 In a coincidence number sequence, if pseudo-prime coincidence numbers exist, there can only be two such numbers, neither more nor fewer.

3 Fundamental Results

The prime coincidence numbers in a coincidence number sequence are precisely the even numbers in Goldbach's conjecture a). Therefore, if it can be proved that: In every coincidence number sequence with any even number n greater than 4 as the halt number, there exist prime coincidence numbers in each, then Goldbach's conjecture a) is proved to hold.

Because in any coincidence number sequence:

The total count of prime coincidence numbers = the total count of coincident numbers - the total count of even coincident numbers - the total count of composite coincident numbers - 2 (the total count of pseudo-prime coincidence numbers).

Thus, in any coincidence number sequence, from the total count of coincident numbers, removing all even coincident numbers, composite coincident numbers, and pseudo-prime coincidence numbers, then what remains are precisely the prime coincidence numbers.

The following seeks to prove whether in every coincidence number sequence there invariably exist prime coincidence numbers. First, conduct the argumentation of the following three lemmas:

Explanatory Note:

To prove the Goldbach conjecture, this paper proposes for the first time the novel concept of "fractional multiples," which has not yet existed in number theory. Concurrently, it redefines and explicitly expands the definition of "multiple": In this paper, the term "multiple" denotes the numerical value of the quotient, such as that obtained by dividing n by k in Lemma 1. This quotient comprises both: an integer part greater than or equal to 1, termed "integer multiples" in this paper, and a fractional part less than 1, termed "fractional multiples" in this paper. Therefore, the "multiple" as defined herein encompasses both integer multiples and fractional multiples. This definition applies exclusively within the scope of this paper.

Lemma 1: Let k be an arbitrary odd prime number. In the consecutive natural numbers from 1 to n , since every k consecutive natural numbers necessarily contain exactly one number divisible by k , the multiples of k account for $\frac{1}{k}$ of n . (To ensure computational accuracy, the term "multiples" in this paper includes fractional multiples, not merely integer multiples. This convention applies throughout.)

Proof:

Take two arbitrarily selected natural numbers: one is 10, the other is the prime 3, for

example. How many integer multiples of 3 exist in the consecutive natural numbers from 1 to 10?

By the floor function, $\lfloor \frac{10}{3} \rfloor = 3$ is indisputably correct. Then, how is this result derived?

According to the accepted method of taking the integer part, in the calculation process for this problem, the first step must necessarily obtain the quotient of 10 divided by 3; the second step can then extract the integer part from this quotient.

Now, merely not taking the second step of this calculation process, but only taking the first step of this calculation process, that is: $\frac{10}{3} = 3\frac{1}{3}$. This quotient is the total number of multiples of 3 in the consecutive natural numbers from 1 to 10. The term "multiples" in Lemma 1 means precisely this, including not only the three integer multiples 3, 6, and 9, but also the fractional multiple $\frac{1}{3}$. Therefore, among the consecutive natural numbers from 1 to 10, there are $\frac{10}{3}$ multiples of 3.

If we replace this arbitrarily selected natural number 10 with an arbitrary natural number n , and replace this arbitrarily selected prime 3 with an arbitrary odd prime k , then we obtain:

$$\frac{n}{k} = \frac{1}{k} \times n$$

Therefore, in the consecutive natural numbers starting from 1 to n , the multiples of k account for $\frac{1}{k}$ of n .

Lemma 2: Let k_1, k_2, k_3 be arbitrary distinct prime numbers. Let z be the number of common multiples of k_1 and k_2 among the consecutive natural numbers from 1 to n , and let z' be the number of common multiples of k_1, k_2, k_3 . According to Lemma 1, it can be obtained that:

$$z = \frac{n}{k_1 \times k_2} = \frac{n}{k_1} \times \frac{1}{k_2} = \frac{n}{k_2} \times \frac{1}{k_1}$$

$$z' = \frac{n}{k_1 \times k_2 \times k_3} = \frac{n}{k_1 \times k_2} \times \frac{1}{k_3} = z \times \frac{1}{k_3}$$

The same reasoning holds for common multiples of arbitrary many prime numbers.

Lemma 3: When $x' = x$, $y' = -y$, the equation $ax + by = c$ becomes $ax' = c + by'$.

In this equation $ax' = c + by'$, let a be an arbitrary prime number, b and c be positive integers, with $c < b$ and $(a, b) = 1$. According to Theorem 1.5, all integer solutions of $ax' = c + by'$ are:

$$x' = x = x_0 + bt, y' = -y = -y_0 + at, \text{ where } t = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \dots$$

Remove all negative values of t ; then bt and at are all positive integers or zero. At this time, regardless of whether x_0 and $-y_0$ are negative or positive, we can easily obtain:

$$x' = x'_0 + bt, y' = y'_0 + at, \text{ such that } 0 \leq y'_0 < a.$$

Because in the same set of integer solutions, $x'_0 = \frac{c+by'_0}{a}$, with both numerator and denominator being positive, it follows that $x'_0 > 0$.

If $x' = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, then ax' is a sequence of consecutive integer multiples of a .

If $y' = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$, then $c + by'$ is an arithmetic progression with increasing terms, where the first term is c and the common difference is b .

From the positive integer solutions of the equation $c + by' = ax'$: $y' = y'_0 + at$, with $0 \leq y'_0 < a$, it follows that:

Among all terms of the sequence $c + by'$, within the first consecutive a terms there is one integer multiple of a , and likewise within every subsequent consecutive a terms there is also one integer multiple of a . Therefore, the number of multiples of a accounts for $\frac{1}{a}$ of the total number of terms.

3.1 Remove all even coincident numbers

In any coincidence number sequence with any even number n greater than 4 as the halt number, from the corresponding sequences ox and oy , remove all coincident numbers where the integer multiples of 2 are located, then the remaining coincident numbers (denoted as b_2) account for $\frac{1}{2}$ of the total number of coincident numbers.

3.2 Remove All Composite Coincident Numbers

Step 1: remove all multiples of 3 and the coincident numbers where they are located.

Following 3.1, after removing all even coincident numbers, among all remainders in this coincident number sequence, from the corresponding sequences ox and oy respectively, remove the composite numbers among the multiples of 3 and the coincident numbers where they are located. Normally, according to the Eratosthenes sieve method, removing composite numbers that are multiples of 3 should start from 3^2 , removing all composite numbers among the multiples of 3. However, for computational simplicity and accuracy, this paper does not adopt the above approach, but instead, based on Lemma 1, treat all composite numbers among the multiples of 3 as all multiples of 3. Thus,

From the corresponding sequence ox , remove all multiples of 3;

From the corresponding sequence oy , remove all multiples of 3.

By the principle of common multiples, the removed corresponding numbers account for $\frac{1}{3}$ of the total remainders b_2 in each corresponding sequence (proof below). On this basis, respectively remove all of the coincident numbers where these removed corresponding numbers are located, then the ratio of all remaining coincident numbers (denoted as b_3) to the total number of coincident numbers is:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times (1 - \frac{1}{3} \times 2) = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{3}$$

Note: When the halt number n is an integer multiple of 3, all integer multiples of 3 in ox and oy are respectively and reversely corresponding to each other. To keep the resulting ratio formula simple and uniform, it is also necessary to additionally remove an equivalent $\frac{1}{3}$ of the coincident numbers simultaneously in an appropriate manner.

Proof:

Let a_2 be the number of multiples of 2 in n , a_3 the number of multiples of 3, and z_1 the number of common multiples of 2 and 3.

By Lemma 1: $a_2 = \frac{n}{2}$, $a_3 = \frac{n}{3}$

By Lemma 2: $z_1 = \frac{n}{2 \times 3} = \frac{n}{2} \times \frac{1}{3} = \frac{a_2}{3}$

$\therefore a_3 = \frac{n}{3} = \frac{a_2 + b_2}{3} = z_1 + \frac{b_2}{3}$

\therefore Therefore, the removed corresponding numbers respectively account for $\frac{1}{3}$ of the total remainders b_2 in each corresponding sequence.

Step 2: remove all multiples of 5 and the coincident numbers where they are located.

For computational simplicity, treat all composite numbers among the multiples of 5 as

all multiples of 5. Thus, among all remainders in this coincidence number sequence,

from the corresponding sequence ox , remove all multiples of 5;

from the corresponding sequence oy , remove all multiples of 5.

According to the principle of common multiples and Theorem 1.5, the removed corresponding numbers respectively account for $\frac{1}{5}$ of the total remainders b_3 in each corresponding sequence (proof below). On this basis, respectively remove all of the coincident numbers where these removed corresponding numbers are located, then the ratio of all remaining coincident numbers (denoted as b_5) to the total number of coincident numbers is:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{3} \times (1 - \frac{1}{5} \times 2) = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1 \times 3}{3 \times 5}$$

Proof:

Let a_5 be the number of multiples of 5 in n , and let $\frac{b_2}{3} = a'_3$, Then: $a_5 = \frac{n}{5}$,

$$a'_3 = a_3 - z_1.$$

In the first step of Section 3.2, not only were all multiples of 3 removed from both ox and oy , but all reverse-corresponding numbers associated with these multiples of 3 were also simultaneously removed. According to the common multiple principle and Lemma 2, among the removed multiples of 3, those that were also multiples of 5 constituted $\frac{1}{5}$ of the total. Now, among these simultaneously removed reverse-corresponding numbers associated with the multiples of 3, are there any multiples of 5? How many multiples of 5 are there?

After removing all multiples of 2, the remaining integer multiples of 3 in ox and oy are:

3,9,15,21,27, ..., is set to B , expressed as $3 + 6y$

When n is any one in the infinite arithmetic progression $n = 10, 16, 22, \dots$, since $(n - 1)$ is certainly an integer multiple of 3, therefore, in these coincidence number sequences with n as the halt number, the sequences respectively and reversely corresponding to the multiples B of 3 in ox and oy can only be:

1,7,13,19,25, ..., denoted as set A and expressed as $1 + 6y$.

When n is any one in the infinite arithmetic progression $n = 8, 14, 20, \dots$, since $(n - 2)$ is certainly an integer multiple of 3, therefore, in these coincidence number sequences with n as the halt number, the sequences respectively and reversely corresponding to the multiples B of 3 in ox and oy can only be:

5,11,17,23,29, ..., denoted as set C and expressed as $5 + 6y$.

When n is any one in the infinite arithmetic progression $n = 6, 12, 18, \dots$, n is an integral multiple of 3. In these coincidence number sequences with n as the halt number, the multiples of 3 (set B) in ox and oy are all reversely corresponding to each other respectively. Meanwhile, in the same one-third of coincident numbers that are removed simultaneously, the reversely corresponding sequences are A and C respectively.

In sequences A , B , and C : $y = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$.

The number of corresponding numbers in sequences A and C is uniformly denoted by $S(3)$.

Through equations such as $1 + 6y = 5x$, with $(5, 6) = 1$, and from **Lemma 3**, it is known that:

In each of the sequences A , B , and C , among every 5 consecutive terms there is

exactly one integer multiple of 5, and among every 7 consecutive terms there is exactly one integer multiple of 7, and so on.

Therefore, multiples of 5 account for $\frac{1}{5}$ of $S(3)$, and multiples of 7 account for $\frac{1}{7}$ of $S(3)$.

Given:

$$\because a_5 = \frac{n}{5} = \frac{a_2 + a'_3 + S(3) + b_3}{5} = \frac{a_2}{5} + \frac{a'_3}{5} + \frac{S(3)}{5} + \frac{b_3}{5}$$

By the principle of common multiples: Multiples of 5 constitute exactly $\frac{1}{5}$ of a_2 and exactly $\frac{1}{5}$ of a'_3 .

Therefore, these removed corresponding numbers each respectively account for $\frac{1}{5}$ of the all remainders b_3 in their corresponding number sequences.

Step 3: Remove all multiples of 7 and the coincident numbers where they are located.

For computational simplicity, composite numbers within the multiples of 7 are calculated as all multiples of 7. Thus, within all remainders of this coincident number sequence:

From the corresponding sequence ox , remove all multiples of 7;

From the corresponding sequence oy , remove all multiples of 7.

According to the principle of common multiples and Theorem 1.5, these removed corresponding numbers account for $\frac{1}{7}$ of all remainders b_5 in their respective corresponding sequences (proof provided below). On this basis, by removing all coincident numbers where these removed corresponding numbers reside, the ratio of

all remaining coincident numbers (denoted as b_7) to the total number of coincident numbers is:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1 \times 3}{3 \times 5} \times (1 - \frac{1}{7} \times 2) = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{3 \times 5 \times 7}$$

Proof:

Let a_7 be the number of multiples of 7 in n , and let $\frac{b_3}{5} = a'_5$, Then: $a_7 = \frac{n}{7}$.

In Step 2 of Section 3.2, not only were all multiples of 5 removed from ox and oy respectively, but also those corresponding numbers that are reversely corresponding to the multiples of 5 were removed respectively as well. According to the principle of common multiples and Lemma 2, among these removed multiples of 5, those that are also multiples of 7 account for $\frac{1}{7}$. Then, among these simultaneously removed numbers that are in reverse correspondence with the multiples of 5, are there any multiples of 7? How many multiples of 7 are there? After all multiples of 2 were removed, all remaining integer multiples of 5 in the corresponding sequences ox and oy are respectively:

5,15,25,35,45, \dots , is set to S , expressed as $5 + 10y$.

When n is any one in the infinite arithmetic progression $n = 6,16,26,36,46, \dots$, since $(n - 1)$ is necessarily an integral multiple of 5, therefore, in each of these coincident number sequences with n as the halt number, the sequences respectively and reversely corresponding to the sequence S in ox and oy can only be:

1,11,21,31,41, \dots , denoted as F , expressed as $1 + 10y$.

When n is any one in the infinite arithmetic progression $n = 8,18,28,38,48, \dots$, since $(n - 3)$ is necessarily an integral multiple of 5, therefore, in each of these coincident number sequences with n as the halt number, the sequences respectively

and reversely corresponding to the sequence S in ox and oy can only be:

3,13,23,33,43, \dots , denoted as P , expressed as $3 + 10y$.

When n is any one in the infinite arithmetic progression $n = 12,22,32,42,52, \dots$, since $(n-7)$ is necessarily an integral multiple of 5, therefore, in each of these coincident number sequences with n as the halt number, the sequences respectively and reversely corresponding to the sequence S in ox and oy can only be:

7,17,27,37,47, \dots , denoted as M , expressed as $7 + 10y$.

When n is any one in the infinite arithmetic progression $n = 14,24,34,44,54, \dots$, since $(n-9)$ is necessarily an integral multiple of 5, therefore, in each of these coincident number sequences with n as the halt number, the sequences respectively and reversely corresponding to the sequence S in ox and oy can only be:

9,19,29,39,49, \dots , denoted as U , expressed as $9 + 10y$.

However, through Step 1 of Section 3.2, all multiples of 3 and their coincident numbers have been removed. Thus, after removing all multiples of 3 and their corresponding numbers from sequences S , F , P , M , and U , the remaining sequences are denoted as s' , f' , p' , m' , and u' respectively.

When n is any one in the infinite arithmetic progression $n = 10,20,30,40,50, \dots$, n is an integer multiple of 5. In each coincident number sequence with such an n as the halt number, the multiples of 5 in ox and oy are corresponding to each other in reverse directions. After removing all coincident numbers that contain multiples of 5, among the additional $\frac{1}{5}$ of coincident numbers removed simultaneously, the corresponding numbers are the reverse-direction sequences f' and u' , or p' and m' .

In sequences S , F , P , M , and U : let $y = 0,1,2,3, \dots$.

Through equations such as $1 + 10y = 3x$, with $(3,10) = 1$, Lemma 3 implies that in each sequence S, F, P, M, U : Among every 7 consecutive terms, there is exactly one integer multiple of 7. Therefore, multiples of 7 constitute exactly $\frac{1}{7}$ of the count of corresponding numbers in each sequence S, F, P, M , and U .

By the principle of common multiples: Among the removed multiples of 3 in each sequence S, F, P, M , and U , those simultaneously divisible by 7 constitute exactly $\frac{1}{7}$. From the proof of Step 2: Among the corresponding numbers reverse-corresponding to these removed multiples of 3, multiples of 7 constitute exactly $\frac{1}{7}$.

Thus, multiples of 7 constitute exactly $\frac{1}{7}$ of the count of corresponding numbers in each sequence s', f', p', m' , and u' .

It is evident that: The number of corresponding numbers in s' is precisely a'_5 .

In the sequences f', p', m' , and u' , the count of corresponding numbers in each sequence is uniformly denoted as $S(5)$.

From the decomposition:

$$a_7 = \frac{n}{7} = \frac{a_2 + a'_3 + S(3) + a'_5 + S(5) + b_5}{7} = \frac{a_2}{7} + \frac{a'_3}{7} + \frac{S(3)}{7} + \frac{a'_5}{7} + \frac{S(5)}{7} + \frac{b_5}{7}$$

By the principle of common multiples and Lemma 3:

Multiples of 7 occupy $\frac{1}{7}$ of $a_2, a'_3, S(3)$, and a'_5 .

Hence, these removed corresponding numbers respectively account for $\frac{1}{7}$ of all remainders b_5 in the corresponding sequence.

...the remaining steps are the same in method and reasoning.

Continuing this process in this way, among all remainders of this coincidence number sequence, from the corresponding sequences ox and oy respectively, remove all multiples of the consecutive primes $3, 5, 7, 11, \dots, k$ one by one and separately. On this basis, then separately remove all the coincident numbers that contain each of these removed corresponding numbers.

By Theorem 1.3, under the condition that prime k does not exceed \sqrt{n} (where k is the largest prime number not exceeding \sqrt{n}), all composite coincident numbers in the coincidence number sequence are thereby eliminated, then the ratio of all remaining coincident numbers to the total number of coincident numbers is:

$$D = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 7 \cdots \times (k-2)}{3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 11 \cdots \times k}$$

3.3 Further Removal of the Two Pseudo-Prime Coincidence Numbers

Because a coincidence number sequence is formed by the reverse-corresponding numbers from the corresponding sequences ox and oy , for any even halt number n , there is always exactly one 1 in each of the ox and oy sequences. Moreover, the corresponding number 1 in ox and the corresponding number 1 in oy always reverse-correspond to the same single number. In coincident numbers across different coincidence number sequences, the number corresponding to 1 may sometimes be prime and sometimes non-prime. Therefore, in a coincidence number sequence: if there are pseudo-prime coincidence numbers, then there can only be 2, neither more nor fewer.

Although some coincidence number sequences contain no pseudo-prime coincidence numbers, for computational simplicity, the calculation is performed under the assumption that every coincidence number sequence contains two pseudo-prime coincidence numbers.

Because after all even coincident numbers and composite coincident numbers are

removed, what remains is precisely the prime coincidence numbers and the pseudo-prime coincidence numbers. Therefore, the aforementioned ratio D is, within any coincidence number sequence with an even number n greater than 4 as the halt number, the ratio of the sum of the counts of prime coincidence numbers and pseudo-prime coincidence numbers to the total number of coincident numbers. Namely:

$$\text{That is: } D = \frac{(\text{Number of remaining prime coincident numbers} + 2)}{\text{Total number of coincident numbers}} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 9 \dots \times (k-2)}{3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 11 \dots \times k}$$

$$\therefore \text{Number of prime coincident numbers} = \text{Total coincident numbers} \times D - 2$$

$$= nD - 2 \quad \text{Substituting } D:$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 9 \dots \times (k-2) \times n}{3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 11 \dots \times k} - 2$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{3 \times 5 \times 9 \times 11 \dots \times n}{3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 11 \dots \times k} - 2 > \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{n}{k} - 2$$

$$\therefore k < \sqrt{n}$$

$$\therefore nD - 2 > \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{n}{k} - 2 > \frac{k}{2} - 2$$

$$\text{For } n \geq 50 : k \geq 7, nD - 2 > \frac{k}{2} - 2 > 1$$

During the process where the prime k tends to infinity alongside the even number n , the relation $\frac{k}{2} - 2 > 1$, holds perpetually.

Numbers greater than $\frac{k}{2} - 2$ are certainly no fewer than $\frac{k}{2} - 2$.

Therefore, in every coincidence number sequence with any even number n starting from 50 and increasing as the halt number, the number of prime coincidence numbers is not less than $\frac{k}{2} - 2$ (taking the integer part), and there is at least one prime

coincidence number in each.

Explanation: Obviously, according to the above practices, while removing all composite coincidence numbers, some prime coincidence numbers will also be removed (proof omitted). However, because the purpose of this paper is not to accurately calculate exactly how many prime coincidence numbers there are in each coincidence number sequence, but rather to verify that in every coincidence number sequence with any even number greater than 4 as the halt number, as long as there are prime coincidence numbers existing in each, no matter how many, as long as it is not less than 1, even if all the remaining prime coincidence numbers are removed, it can still prove that the Goldbach conjecture holds. Therefore, the above practices do not affect the proof of the Goldbach conjecture.

For every even number from 6 to 48, it can be easily verified that it equals the sum of two odd primes:

6=3+3, 8=3+5, 10=3+7, 12=5+7, 14=7+7, 16=5+11, 18=7+11, 20=7+13,
22=5+17, 24=11+13, 26=13+13, 28=11+17, 30=13+17, 32=13+19, 34=17+17,
36=17+19, 38=19+19, 40=11+29, 42=11+31, 44=13+31, 46=17+29, 48=7+41.

Conclusion:

Therefore, any even number greater than 4 can be expressed as the sum of two odd primes

4 Comparative Verification

In one and the same coincidence number sequence with any even number $n > 4$ as the halt number:

In the preceding verification, when k is the largest prime not exceeding \sqrt{n} , using the Eratosthenes sieve method, through verification, the ratio D is obtained.

Now, let p be the largest odd number not exceeding \sqrt{n} . Clearly, $k \leq p$. By employing the modified sieve method and adhering to the same procedural steps used earlier to derive the ratio D , but replacing the consecutive primes starting from 3 up to k with consecutive odd numbers starting from 3 up to p , the ratio D is thereby transformed into the ratio D_p . They are respectively:

$$D = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 9 \cdots \times (k-2)}{3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 11 \cdots \times K}$$

$$D_p = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 9 \cdots \times (p-2)}{3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 9 \times 11 \cdots \times p}$$

These two ratios both represent the ratio of the sum of the remaining prime coincidence numbers and two pseudo-prime coincidence numbers to the total number of coincident numbers, within the same coincidence number sequence with the even number n as the halt number. Comparing these two ratios, the following key differences are evident:

4.1 The denominators of D are entirely contained within the denominators of D_p .

4.2 When $n \geq 82$, $D > D_p$.

All odd multiples (excluding 1) of consecutive primes starting from 3 are certainly contained within the consecutive odd composite numbers starting from 9. The consecutive odd composite numbers 9,15,21,25,27, ... in the denominator of D_p are integer multiples of 3,3,3,5,3, ... respectively. Originally, after removing, one by one and respectively from all remainders in the coincidence number sequence and its two corresponding sequences ox and oy , the multiples of each consecutive prime 3,5,7,11, ... k and their coincident numbers, the ratio D is obtained. Then, D_p is defined on this basis of D by, without justification, further removing again from all remainders in the corresponding sequences ox and oy respectively and in order, according to $\frac{1}{9}, \frac{1}{15}, \frac{1}{21}, \frac{1}{25}, \frac{1}{27}, \dots$ up to $\frac{1}{p}$ when $k \neq p$, the multiples of the primes

3,5,7,11, ... and their coincident numbers once more.

When nothing remains to be subtracted, there is no choice but to perform the subtraction on the prime coincidence numbers.

According to the "Table of the Least Primitive Roots for Primes (within 5000)" in Introduction to Number Theory [3]: When n reaches 118, the number of odd composite numbers already equals the number of odd primes. When n reaches 1120, the number of odd composite numbers is twice that of odd primes. As n tends to infinity, "the ratio of the number of primes to n approaches zero. That is: almost all integers are composite numbers" [3].

Consequently, the larger the value of n , the greater the quantity of coincident numbers forcibly subtracted in this manner.

The result of this subtraction is that, within all remainders of $nD_p - 2$, what remains can only be entirely prime coincidence numbers!

$$nD_p - 2 = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 9 \dots \times (P-2) \times n}{3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 9 \times 11 \dots \times P} - 2 = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{n}{p} - 2 > \frac{p}{2} - 2$$

Therefore, in every coincidence number sequence with any even number n starting from 50 and increasing as the halt number, the count of prime coincidence numbers is no less than $\frac{p}{2} - 2$ (taking the integer part), and there is always at least one prime coincidence number.

$$\because k \leq p$$

$$\therefore nD_p - 2 > \frac{p}{2} - 2 \geq \frac{k}{2} - 2$$

Through comparative verification, the preceding verification results are proved to be correct.

For the ratios D and D_p of the same coincident number sequence, among all continuous factors of the ratio D_p , let the largest one be the factor whose denominator is $p = k$, then:

$$nD_p - 2 = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{n}{p} - 2 = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{n}{k} - 2 > \frac{k}{2} - 2 \quad \textcircled{1}$$

$$nD - 2 > \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{n}{k} - 2 > \frac{k}{2} - 2 \quad \textcircled{2}$$

Clearly, Equation (1) is more precise than Equation (2).

It is common knowledge: Although the number of primes is infinite, the total count of all primes discovered worldwide thus far is far from unlimited! Finding any prime number larger than the largest prime currently known is immensely difficult! Given all existing methods for discovering primes, it is fundamentally impossible to identify arbitrarily large primes!

Consequently, consider the previously derived result: Within every coincidence number sequence ending at an arbitrary even number n , the number of prime coincidence numbers is no less than $\frac{k}{2} - 2$. In this result: When k is any prime number currently known, the specific value of $\frac{k}{2} - 2$ can be readily computed. When k is one of those primes yet to be discovered, k lacks a specific value, rendering the computation of a specific value for $\frac{k}{2} - 2$ impossible.

Unquestionably, during the progression of natural numbers from 1 toward infinity, regardless of how large the natural numbers extend, every even number n in this natural number sequence possesses a concrete value! Using established methods, the precise value of each \sqrt{n} is readily computable. Consequently, the largest odd number P not exceeding \sqrt{n} can always be determined, and thus the concrete value of $\frac{P}{2} - 2$ is invariably computable.

This implies that the result — in every coincidence number sequence, the count of prime coincidence numbers is no less than $\frac{p}{2} - 2$ — circumvents the problem of unknown primes. Hence, adopting this result is superior.

Through comparative verification, this further proves that the Goldbach conjecture a) is correct.

5. Proof of Goldbach Conjecture b):

Unquestionably, every even number greater than 4 is contained within the following infinite, arithmetically increasing sequence of even numbers:

6,8,10,...

Denote this sequence as H , represented by $6+2y$, where $y = 0,1,2,3, \dots$.

Adding the odd prime 3 to each term of this infinite sequence of consecutive even numbers yields the following infinite sequence of consecutive odd numbers starting from 9:

9,11,13,...

Denote this sequence as G , represented by $9 + 2y$, where $y = 0,1,2,3, \dots$.

It is evident that every odd number greater than 7 is contained within this sequence.

The preceding proof has established that every even number in sequence H can be expressed as the sum of two odd primes.

Moreover, every odd number in sequence G is equal to an even number from sequence H plus the odd prime 3.

Consequently, every odd number greater than 7 can be expressed as the sum of three odd primes. Therefore, Goldbach conjecture b) holds true.

Thus, the present paper has furnished a complete proof that the Goldbach conjecture holds true.

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Statements and Declarations

Author Contributions

Yao Xingzhi is the sole author and is responsible for all aspects of this work, including: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Validation, Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing, and Supervision.

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